

EFFECT OF REWARD POLICY, AND ORGANIZATION COMMUNICATION ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR IN KENYA: A CASE STUDY OF NATIONAL REGISTRATION BUREAU, NAIROBI

^{1*}Hassan Fatuma Khalif, ^{2*}Edna Bonareri

¹MBA Student: Management University of Africa

P. O. Box. 29677-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

² Lecturer Management University of Africa

P. O. Box. 29677-00100, Nairobi, Kenya

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Abstract: The main objective of this study was to evaluate the influence of reward policy, and organization communication on employee performance in the public sector in Kenya with a consideration of the National Registration Bureau, Nairobi. Specifically, this study established effects of reward policy, organizational communication, job security and training on performance of civil servants at NRB. The study used equity theory, attribution theory, Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs Theory model and Social Cognitive theory. A descriptive research design was used for the investigation. The investigation targeted the 1,918 employees who work at NRB in Nairobi County. The researcher used Krejcie and Morgan formula to determine sample size for study. A questionnaire served as the instrument for acquiring data in this investigation. Pilot examination was conducted in to determine the validity and reliability of the instrument. The statistics were modified, encoded, and imported into SPSS version 26.0 for analysis. Multiple regression model was used to ascertain how parameters relate to one another. The study revealed that a change in reward policy, and organization communication significantly impacted employee performance. A 24.5% change in reward policy results in a 0.245-unit change, while a 34.5% change in communication results in a 0.345-unit change. These findings suggested that adjusting these factors can significantly impact employee performance, highlighting the importance of effective communication and training in enhancing employee performance. The study concluded that a well-structured reward policy, and organization communication are important for improving employee performance in Kenya's public sector. The study recommended the following; Public-sector organizations should emphasize the creation and execution of a clear and equitable incentive strategy that is consistent with employee contributions and industry benchmarks. The study recommended that a bottom-up method to communication be implemented in Kenya's public sector; this can improve communication between managers and their subordinates, ultimately improving employee performance. Organizations should establish clear and open personnel policies that promote job stability and effectively convey them to all employees. The report suggests doing the investigation again in different parastatals to facilitate generalization of the research findings.

Keywords: Reward Policy, Organization Communication, Employee Performance And Public Sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Employee performance in the public sector is an essential component for the efficient provision of operations as well as the overall functionality of government operations. High-performing public sector employees contribute to better governance, increased efficiency, and improved public trust (Perry & Hondeghem, 2019). Globally, countries employ various strategies to enhance public sector performance, including performance management systems, professional development initiatives, and incentive-based approaches. These strategies aim to create a motivated workforce capable of meeting the demands of public service (OECD, 2020).

In the United States, performance management systems are integral to the public sector. Initiatives like the Government Performance and Results Act (GPRA) focus on setting clear objectives and regularly evaluating employee outcomes to ensure accountability and efficiency. Performance-based budgeting and merit-based promotions are also used to motivate employees and align their performance with organizational goals (Boyne, 2020). Similarly, in Canada, the public sector employs a results-oriented management approach, emphasizing transparency and accountability to enhance employee performance (OECD, 2020). European countries, particularly in Scandinavia, emphasize the well-being and motivation of public sector employees as key drivers of performance. Countries like Denmark, Sweden, and Norway implement comprehensive work-life balance policies, continuous professional development, and participatory management styles to foster high performance among employees (Christensen & Læg Reid, 2020). In the UK, performance-related pay and rigorous performance appraisals are employed to align individual performance with broader organizational objectives (Bach, 2020).

In Asia, countries such as Singapore and South Korea have made significant strides in public sector performance. Singapore's public sector is renowned for its efficiency and low corruption levels, largely due to a competency-based framework for assessing and enhancing employee performance (Quah, 2021). South Korea employs performance-based incentives and career development programs to maintain high productivity levels among public servants (Kim & Hong, 2022). These approaches emphasize the importance of a motivated and skilled workforce in achieving high performance. In Africa, public sector performance faces unique challenges, including limited resources, political instability, and corruption. Efforts to improve performance often focus on capacity building, anti-corruption measures, and reforms aimed at enhancing accountability and transparency. For instance, Rwanda's performance contracts (Imihigo) have led to significant enhancements in service delivery and accountability (World Bank, 2021). However, many African countries still struggle with inefficiencies and low motivation among public sector employees (Afrobarometer, 2022). In the East African Community (EAC) area, nations like Tanzania, Uganda, and Kenya are making efforts to improve public sector performance. Initiatives such as performance contracts, capacity-building programs, and anti-corruption campaigns are being implemented. In Uganda, the Results-Oriented Management (ROM) framework links individual performance with institutional goals to enhance service delivery (Kiwunika, 2021). Tanzania's Big Results Now (BRN) initiative focuses on key sectors to drive performance improvements and achieve national development goals (United Republic of Tanzania, 2021). Kenya's public sector is pivotal for the country's socio-economic development, having an effect on vital sectors including buildings, medical care, and academia. Despite implementing performance contracts and strategic planning, the sector faces challenges like corruption, inadequate compensation, and bureaucratic inefficiencies. According to Transparency International (2023), Kenya ranks 123rd out of 180 countries in the Corruption Perception Index, indicating significant governance issues. Efforts by the Kenyan government to enhance accountability and productivity are ongoing, but the sector continues to grapple with inefficiencies (Republic of Kenya, 2022).

Staff productivity is significantly influenced by job satisfaction. It encompasses various elements like the workplace, compensation, career possibilities and stability in employment advancement. High job satisfaction leads to increased motivation, reduced absenteeism, and improved overall performance (Judge et al., 2019). In the public sector, enhancing job satisfaction can directly impact employee performance by fostering a motivated and committed workforce. In Kenya, job satisfaction among public sector employees is mixed. While some employees appreciate job security and the social impact of their work, many are dissatisfied with working conditions, remuneration, and career advancement opportunities. A study by the Kenya School of Government (2021) revealed that over 60% of public sector workers weren't happy with their salaries or their job environments, adversely affecting their performance and commitment. Efforts to improve job

satisfaction include salary reviews, professional development programs, and better working conditions, although budget constraints and systemic inefficiencies often limit their effectiveness.

1.1.1 Reward Policy

An organized reward policy is essential for improving employee performance in the public sector. Reward policies that effectively recognize and compensate employees' efforts lead to higher motivation, job satisfaction, and overall productivity. According to Mwangi (2020), public sector employees in Kenya often feel undervalued due to inadequate and inconsistent reward systems. This inadequacy not only affects their morale but also their performance. Comprehensive reward policies should include both financial and non-monetary rewards like bonuses and increases in pay, recognition programs, and career development opportunities. When employees feel appreciated and fairly rewarded, they are more likely to be committed to their roles and perform better (Armstrong & Taylor, 2023).

1.1.2 Organizational Communication

Effective organizational communication is another key factor influencing employee performance in the public sector. Clear, consistent, and transparent communication helps align individual employee goals with the organization's objectives, thereby enhancing overall performance. Kamau and Omari (2018) highlight that poor communication within Kenya's public sector often leads to misunderstandings, reduced efficiency, and a lack of direction among employees. Regular and open communication channels, feedback mechanisms, and participatory decision-making processes can mitigate these issues. When employees are well-informed and engaged in the organization's activities, their performance and productivity improve significantly (Robbins & Judge, 2019).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The performance of employees in Kenya's public sector, specifically at the National Registration Bureau (NRB) in Nairobi, falls short of expectations. Despite the implementation of various performance enhancement strategies, the actual output remains suboptimal. Employees frequently face issues such as delays, inefficiencies and dissatisfaction with services delivered, as evidenced by numerous complaints (Wambugu, 2021). This has led to growing concerns about the overall productivity of public sector workers, which directly impacts the public who rely on these services. One major issue is the inadequacy of reward policies, which fail to motivate employees effectively (Mwangi, 2020). In contrast to private sector practices, the public sector's approach to recognizing and compensating contributions is often insufficient. Additionally, bureaucratic hurdles hamper organizational communication, leading to misalignment between employee goals and organizational objectives (Kamau & Omari, 2018). The lack of transparency and clarity in communication further exacerbates this problem.

Job security is another key concern. Employees face uncertainty due to political interference and frequent policy inconsistencies, which undermine their morale and commitment (Njenga, 2019). This insecurity reduces their willingness to invest effort into their roles, knowing that external factors may jeopardize their positions. Training programs, which are crucial for skill development and maintaining high performance, are also poorly structured and underfunded (Mungai, 2021). Without adequate training, employees are ill-equipped to perform their duties effectively, leading to further inefficiencies in service delivery. These issues contribute to the overall inefficiency of the NRB, affecting the public's access to essential services like the issuance of national identification cards. Delays in such services can disrupt citizens' ability to access healthcare, education, and participate in democratic processes, such as voting (Mutua, 2021). If left unaddressed, these underlying problems will continue to erode public trust in government institutions and compromise the quality of services provided by the public sector (Njeru, 2020).

Although several studies have investigated aspects of employee performance in Kenya's public sector, there remains a gap in understanding how specific factors like reward policies, organizational communication, job security, and training collectively influence performance within the NRB (Oduor, 2019; Karani, 2020). The aim of the present research was to close this gap by evaluating these factors and their impact on employee performance at the NRB in Nairobi. By adopting a comprehensive approach, this research provided actionable insights that can inform policy and strategic interventions aimed at enhancing employee performance in the public sector.

1.3 Objectives

- i) To evaluate how reward policy affects performance of employees in the public sector in Kenya

ii) To examine the effect of organizational communication on performance of employees in the public sector in Kenya

1.4 Justification of the study

Theoretically, knowing the connection between job satisfaction as well as productivity among employees adds to the larger subject of behavioral economics by shedding light on how internal and extrinsic motivators influence worker productivity. This knowledge is critical for academics and HR professionals seeking to create frameworks that explain employee behavior in public-sector entities. This study's findings will add to current ideas on work satisfaction, career accomplishment, and organizational behavior, offering a more complete information of the elements that affect the productivity of employees. From a policy standpoint, the findings of this study are critical for developing successful strategies for managing human resources in the public sector. The NRB administration and other government organizations may use the research findings to develop policies that establish a supportive work environment, increasing job satisfaction and retention among civil workers. By answering crucial concerns about staff retention and motivation, the study contributes to the creation of policies that connect with the 2030 Agenda and Millennium Development Goals, resulting in enhanced public sector performance and service delivery.

Practically, the study's findings will help guide organizational approaches targeted at increasing staff productivity and well-being. By identifying job satisfaction variables and their influence on performance, Kenyan public sector firms may execute focused interventions to increase employee engagement and productivity. These behaviours not only result in a more engaged staff, but they also increase administrative effectiveness. Furthermore, the study serves as a significant reference for future research, providing a strong dataset and analysis that may guide continuing efforts to improve employee satisfaction and performance in a variety of organizational situations.

2. THEORETICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature Review

The study utilized equity theory of motivation as the anchor theory, then attribution theory Maslow's hierarchy of human needs theory and social cognitive career theory.

2.1.1 Equity Theory of Motivation

John Adams is credited with developing the hypothesis in 1963. The ratio of an employee's job inputs to job outputs is thought to affect how satisfied they are with their employment. The idea centers on determining if the managers' allocation of incentives among collaborators is just and equitable. Workers frequently contrast their benefits with those of other comparable categories (Bell, Kennebrew, & Blyden, 2015). In order to benefit both the workers and the organization they are employed for, individuals' inputs as well as outputs need to be coordinated. This symbiotic connection is good since it helps both the organization through better output and the personnel through better incentives. Offering greater pay, recognizing and acknowledging the worker's exceptional performance, and assisting them in advancing their careers are all appropriate ways to show appreciation for their effort, hard work, talent, and capabilities. The input-output balance must be preserved if fulfillment at work is to be attained. According to the hypothesis, the motivation of a worker is directly influenced by the rewards they obtain for finishing a task. According to Mwiti Kainga, (2021), equity theory may be used to explain how reward systems affect employment outcomes.

This framework is used to explain how workers' perceptions of how appropriately and fairly they are being compensated in connection to their dedication to their company's development. The workers take into account how other workers doing comparable job in other organizations are compensated (Mwiti Kainga, 2021), When there occurs a feeling of unfairness in the proportions of the pay paid to the work produced by the worker, then the sensation of being underpaid will set up and then won't be any incentive. According to Mehreza, & Bakria, (2019) employee perception in accordance with equity theory may cause actions that have a detrimental impact on the entire business if there is a sense of unfairness in the organization's incentive structure. The worker can potentially just quit their employment. According to equity theory, incentives in an organizational setting will have a big impact on the workforce (Mehreza, & Bakria, S2019).

According to the equity hypothesis (Adams, 1963), a person's motivation to labor is influenced by what they believe to be fair in comparison to others. Thus, this framework illuminates the fundamental ideas that underlie the use of rewards for efficiency, particularly incentives and other kinds of efficiency-related compensation, in affecting the success of organizations. In response to this anguish, attempts are made to reestablish equity throughout the partnership. Participants

become unsatisfied with the connection when they notice unfairness and either want to end the partnership or achieve equity by changing the results or contributions. Individuals are content with and dedicated to partnerships that are equal (Shin, 2016). According to the notion, government officials' job satisfaction is related to their anticipation of earning compensation proportionate to the work they put in forth in their labor. According to Nzyoka, & Orwa, (2016), how workers anticipate from their place of employment may be compared to their results; if they believe their inputs are bigger than their outcomes, they get depressed. In order to accommodate the requirements and preferences of every staff member and lessen perceived disparity, employees performing identical jobs should be compensated similarly. One of the problems with the equity theory is that it only takes into account how people perceive their level of work satisfaction, leaving out other important motivational elements. It is nearly impossible to measure the link between the input-output ratio and the way that people perceive their work (Nzyoka, & Orwa, 2016).

In application to this study, this theory was related to reward policy and communication variables of this study. Employees are driven by what they see as a fair reward policy. Therefore, in accordance with the equity theory, personnel should get fair compensation in order to reduce their feeling of unfairness.

2.1.2 Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs Theory

Among the most common hypotheses of psychological drive is Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs. Maslow's Hierarchy of Human Needs Theory was developed by Maslow (1943). The notion of the hierarchy of human desires states that workers are motivated by five different sorts of needs: physiological, security, social, self-actualization, and self-esteem. Physiological requirements are the highest-level needs, according to Maslow (1943). These are represented in an organization's demand for a foundation of revenue, adequate warmth, and enough air to guarantee a comfortable life. The safety demands, which include the desire for safety and protection from harm, come next. Safety needs in the workplace refer to the requirements for secure employment, perks, and safe occupations. Social needs include the need to engage with others and to have a sense of love and belonging (Trivedi, & Mehta, 2019).

These wants are a reflection of the urge to be liked, to have friends, to belong to a group, and to be regarded by one's peers. These demands have an impact on how much an employee wants to get along with coworkers, participate in workgroups, and have excellent relationships with supervisors in the workplace. Esteem requirements subsequently emerge, including the need for respect and the need for attention, acknowledgment, success, and admiration, all of which are influenced by a person's standing reputation. Organizational esteem demands are a reflection of a need for recognition, increased accountability, high status, and gratitude for organizational achievements (Trivedi, & Mehta, 2019).

Ultimately, the drive for self-realization is linked to the aspiration of realizing one's whole capacity. The goal of self-realization is satisfaction; it serves as inspiration for individuals to develop artistically and individually as well as to find purpose in their job. They are linked to realizing one's potential, honing one's craft, and developing oneself. Within the company, requirements for self-realization may be met by offering opportunities for personal development, encouraging innovation, and offering learning. People strive for development, success, and advancement in order to attain this (Dharmanegara, Sitiari, & Adelina, 2016). Thus, this theory was put to use in the investigation to look at the different methods of reward policies and communication in utilize and how they fit into the framework of expectations for civil servants. This theory also looked at how these expectations influence how these employees behave, which in consequently influences how efficiently people function for the company.

2.1.3 Goal Setting Theory

Ryan's (1970) premise that goals or objectives drive human behavior has a significant impact on the goal-setting theory. Information asymmetry characterizes all relationships between a principle and an agent (Jensen & Meckling, 2006; Feess, 2004). Since the employer cannot always keep an eye on workers' efforts, there are several things that must be done to encourage the workforce. Setting objectives is a good method to stay motivated. Numerous experimental investigations have demonstrated that goal-setting has a significant impact on human behavior and, as a result, alters performance (Bandura & Cervone, 2009; LaPorte & Nath, 2010). This is valid for varied activities, participant groups, and experimental environments.

Establishing performance levels consciously in order to achieve desired results is known as goal setting. According to this goal-setting approach, motivation stems from the desire and purpose to accomplish a goal (Locke & Latham, 2006). When people or groups discover that their present performance is falling short of what is expected of them, they usually get

inspired to put in more effort or adjust their approach. This theory suggested that an individual's life objectives impact their learning, making it important to the research. The goal-setting hypothesis states that people concentrate their efforts on accomplishing their goals, which will affect their performance. It makes the argument that specific, challenging goals combined with sufficient feedback result in increased and improved task performance. This theory explained training's viability.

2.1.4 Social Cognitive Career Theory

This theory was developed by Robert Lent et al in 1994. They are linked to realizing one's potential, honing one's craft, and developing themselves. The requirements for self-realization may be satisfied inside the organization by offering opportunities for developing oneself, encouraging creativity, and offering instruction for advancement. People strive for development, success, and advancement in order to attain this (Liang, Lai, & Chang, 2021). Thus, these hypotheses were put to use in the investigation to look at the different methods of payment in utilize and how they fit into the framework of demands for civil servants. These theories also looked at how these demands influence how these staff members behave, which in turn affects how well they carry out for the company (Liang, Lai, & Chang, 2021).

Patfield, Gore, & Harris, (2023) narrowed the focus to just personal growth in the framework of professional development. This is an idea that managers might use to keep talent. Career growth, as stated by Ayodo, (2022), is motivated by self-efficacy, or the conviction that one is capable of completing a significant task. Goals and outcome expectancies, or the notion that starting a given activity will produce the intended result, determine the degree of accomplishment. According to Schoenfeld, Segal, & Borgia, (2017), someone is more probable to relate to define steps to achieve goals if they feel confidence in their skills. Organizations may easily retain talent when they put in place strategies to improve motivation. Liang, Lai, & Chang, (2021) claims that the idea links individual failure to a lack of expertise and knowledge that is seen to be acquirable. This theory was related to employee training that is one of the study variables.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

An empirical literature review examines previous studies and research findings on a specific topic, offering a comprehensive analysis of existing knowledge. It helps identify gaps, validate theories, and assess the relevance of various factors influencing the research focus.

2.2.1 Reward policy and performance of employees

The impact of employee reward and work satisfaction on organizational performance was studied by Orajaka (2021) in selected public institutions in the South East of Nigeria. In order to collect data from five (5) states in Nigeria, the investigation's methodology was survey-based. and a questionnaire. All nonacademic employees of the selected institutions provided the primary data that was obtained from the aforementioned states. To find the significant association between the variables, the information was examined using Mean Likert, statistical descriptions, and correlation tools. Subsequently, the research demonstrated a statistically noteworthy positive association between the nonacademic personnel at the institution and employee performance. To determine the association between worker efficiency, which is a variable that is dependent, and rewards for workers, which are an independent variable, Atambo et al. (2019) used a descriptive technique based on an association design. The findings of the research showed that employee incentives significantly improved individual as well as organizational results. In contemporary times, companies use an extensive array of pertinent and fitting rewards to motivate staff members to maximize their abilities and put in more work. Establishes based on results and bonus payments are a couple of the incentive types that are employed (Chepkirui & Atambo, 2024).

Ngwa et al. (2019) investigated the impact of a reward system on employee performance at selected industrial enterprises in Cameroon's Littoral area. Five hundred thirty-eight workers from a workforce of 5046 workers at ten carefully chosen industrial businesses in the Cameroon Littoral Region were surveyed for this study. The sample was selected using the Cochran's technique for an extremely small sample at an accuracy level of 95%. The main form of data for the research project was the initial information, which was gathered via a survey. The results showed that revenue sharing considerably raised staff dedication in manufacturing firms, flat-rate structures considerably reduced employee workplace

principles in the same organizations, and reward schemes for negotiations greatly improved employee cohesion in the same organizations. The study discovered a favorable correlation between worker efficiency and reward schemes.

According to a survey conducted by Onyekwelu et al. (2020) among Nigerian banks, pay policies boost employee engagement, which in turn boosts output. The empirical research by (Kadir et al., 2019) supports these findings. To determine if the university's pay policies and instructors' output were related, the investigators spoke with eighty College teachers. They came to the conclusion that the pay policies had a direct bearing on how well lecturers performed.

The effect of incentives on employee productivity in Nigeria was investigated by Ogohi (2019), using surveys for data collection and a descriptive research approach. Their research proved that incentives and production were positively correlated. The study also found that including employees in the process of achieving organizational performance is crucial for motivating them, since an organization cannot function without their cooperation. They recommended that a unit be established to examine matters related to incentives that may improve productivity. However, the Nigerian setting in which their study was conducted may differ from the Kenyan situation. Another research by Kalaluka (2020) focused on Simba International School in Ndola, Zambia, and attempted to evaluate the effect of management awards on staff performance. The study targeted thirty employees and using a descriptive research approach. In order to gather primary data, questionnaires were distributed. Their research revealed a number of motivating elements that affect worker performance, including as rewards, acknowledgment, employment stability, advancement, business loyalty, favorable working circumstances, and gentle punishment. It was discovered that staff performance was favourably impacted by these motivating elements. The author recommended that businesses provide fundamental guidelines for the appropriate creation of employee incentive programs in light of the inadequate design of many current incentive programs. However, the Zambian setting in which their study was conducted may differ from the Kenyan context.

2.2.2 Organizational communication and performance of employees

Studies on employee performance and organizational communication were carried out by Weldeghebriel (2020) at several major industrial companies in Eritrea. Through the use of purposive sampling on 21 workers and proportional stratified random sample on 267 employees, the study sought to comprehend the inner workings of significant industrial enterprises in Eritrea. Questionnaires and interviews were employed to collect and then evaluate statistically utilizing both inductive and descriptive methods. Thematic analysis of the qualitative data was conducted, and theoretical notions were triangulated with the data. Results of the research demonstrate a extremely noteworthy association between worker performance and communication patterns, worker performance and communication structure, worker performance and communication medium, and worker performance and communication atmosphere. The study concluded that interactions structures, interaction framework, communicating mediums, and communication climate have a direct influence on worker efficiency in the selected large industrial businesses in Eritrea.

The impact of organizational communication on worker performance in Kenyan county governments was investigated by Ndung'u (2023), focusing on a case study of Laikipia. The study used organizational control and social exchange theories to examine 267 appointed staff members and 23 elected members of the Laikipia County Assembly. Interviews with MCAs and CEC members as well as semi-structured questionnaires yielded a sample size of 168 responses. Pilot research including 17 employees of CGL, or 10% of the sample population, was carried out. With SPSS Release 24, a variety of regression analyses were carried out and descriptive data were displayed using frequencies and percentages. Utilizing content analysis, qualitative data was examined. The findings demonstrated that, at a p value of .002, a change in leadership communication greatly enhanced worker performance by 0.680 times.

In the Kenyan telecommunications sector, Syallow (2019) investigated the impact of organizational communication on worker job satisfaction. The study examined communication patterns inside a system and concentrated on three telecommunications companies in Nairobi County, Kenya. There was little research on job satisfaction and organizational communication in Kenya, and the sample size was restricted to 8% of workers. A design that was expressive in nature was employed in the study, and 333 survey questionnaires were completed and submitted. Quantitative data were examined using inferential and descriptive statistics using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (SPSS). According to the report, the majority of workers in Kenya's telecom sector are conversant with organizational communication. In order to foster a unified corporate identity, management ought to raise staff awareness of the company's philosophies and tactics, which will boost commitment and job satisfaction. To enhance task-related

procedures, departmental reporting, and individual performance throughout the company, the research suggests promoting vertical, horizontal, and diagonal communication.

2.2.3 Employee Performance

The relationship between employee earnings and performance procedures was examined by Okoli et al. (2020) in several public universities in Southeast Nigeria. The study's findings led to the selection of the descriptive research strategy. A meticulously designed survey was employed. to get data. Both employee recognition and work satisfaction were shown to have a significant positive correlation with employee participation and distributes equality. The research project was conducted in Nigeria, which has a distinct climate from Kenya. According to Narayanamurthy and Tortorella (2021), the pandemic suggested significant adjustments to the way businesses operate, impacting the schedules and activities of their staff. The pandemic has caused a number of changes to the work environment for employees, including social isolation, travel bans and limitations, and virtual working arrangements. (2020, Harter). Additionally, some companies decided to implement wage reductions and layoffs, which has raised economic loss and job instability, making employees feel more insecure and affecting their performance. These modifications have limited the continuation of previous pre-COVID-19 procedures and brought about behavioral shifts in employees that can go from transient to permanent

The impact of compensation schemes on staff productivity was examined by Cheruiyot and Kalei (2020) at a public university in Kericho County, Kenya. A cross-sectional technique was used for this investigation. Data were collected using surveys, and the results were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The study's findings show a clear relationship between worker performance and the compensation scheme. The study's conclusions imply that the main engine powering government operations is motivated personnel.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

This investigation employed a descriptive research design. The aforementioned research design facilitates the investigation's attempt to determine if the variables at a given moment in time have a meaningful correlation (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2019). A descriptive design is one whose primary concerns are "what, how, and who," which is the focus of this investigation study, as stated by Creswell and Clark (2016). Blumberg et al. (2018) indicate that the goal of study methodology is to provide data that would enable the results to be generalized.

3.2 Target Population

The population being investigated consisted of the target population, which was the personnel of the National Registration Bureau in Nairobi County. The 1,918 personnel at different levels of management who are now employed by the Registration Bureau in the area made up the research's population. Workers at the managerial level were chosen for this investigation because they possess the knowledge that is required for this investigation.

Table 1: Target Population

Category	Target population	Percentage
Executive	202	10.5%
Managerial	769	40.1%
Operational Team	947	49.4%
Total	1,918	100

Source: National Registration Bureau (2024)

3.3 Sample and sampling technique

The sample size was determined as follows, utilizing the Morgan and Krejcie methodology, estimating the error by 5% and providing a ninety-five percent confidence interval:

$$S = \frac{x^2 NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + x^2 P(1 - P)}$$

S = the required sample size

X² = the Chi-square table value for freedom of one degree at the 95% confidence level, or 3.841)

N = Populace proportions

P = Population percentage (0.50 is used; this is the highest percentage)

1-P = expected failure rate in %

d² = square of the maximum tolerance for error between the sample proportion and the real percentage (in this case, 5%). Considering a population of 1,918) The technique yields 320 workers as the sample population.

3.4 Instruments

A questionnaire was used to collect primary data for thus study. The questionnaire was created with the investigation's objectives in mind and includes closed-ended questions. The research project was able to collect more spontaneous responses by using closed-ended questions, which enabled more useful suggestions.

3.5 Pilot Study

To determine the validity and reliability of the instrument, the investigation did a pilot test. According to Cooper and Schindler (2008), the primary goal of a pilot research was to identify any discrepancies in the questions, assess answer uniformity, and ascertain the validity of the results. Pilot testing, as described by Dawson (2002), aids researchers in determining if the survey yielded the anticipated findings. A pre-test sample of 32 respondents, from Kenya Bureau of Standards were used in this investigation. As a general guideline, the sample in pilot research should be 10% of the sample size (Kassu, 2019). The pilot examination's results are significant since they help to improve the data gathering instrument prior to its official implementation.

3.6 Data collection procedure

Following the proposal defense, the investigator submitted a request for license from NACOSTI and authorization to do investigation from Management University of Africa. After that, the investigator went to the National Registration Bureau to get permission to collect data and acquaint herself with the investigation setting. The investigator met the director in order to get a letter approving her to continue with the investigation. After receiving the letter authorizing her to conduct the research, she communicated with the administration and HR managers. The supervisors were given a room to use throughout the data collecting process after the investigator asked them to help identify the participants and outlined the essence and goal of the present investigation.

The goal and logic of the study, as well as the respondents' independence and ethics, was explained to them. In order to safeguard their sense of self, privacy, and secrecy, those taking part did not reveal their names. Before proceeding with the study, the investigator first obtained the participants' agreement and the investigator gave them the survey to fill out. The data was gathered in ten working days. Each participant got the surveys from the examiner personally. Following the completion of the surveys and their return for analysis, the investigator scheduled a meeting to debrief to express gratitude to the participants and discuss any concerns with the investigation. To protect information, the gathered data was placed in a sealed bag, and they were tightly sealed. To guarantee true information from the participants, the investigator was truthful in reporting the results.

3.7 Data Analysis and Presentation

Kothari (2009) states information analysis as examining obtained information and drawing conclusions and deductions from it. Quantitative data was field edited to ensure correctness and authenticity. So as to guarantee the accuracy of the data, every filled questionnaire was examined for errors and inconsistencies. For statistical evaluation, the data was modified, encoded, and imported into SPSS version 25.0. After that, it was examined using both descriptive and inferential indicators to generate measures of dispersion (standard deviation and variance) and central tendency (mean, medium, and mode), as well as to investigate inferential statistics for correlations between the variables. The capacity of the independent variables to be forecasted was explained by the multiple regression approach and Pearson's correlation coefficient in the context of statistical inferences.

The multiple regression model for the study was:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Where;

Y = Employee Performance; X_1 = Reward Policy ; X_2 = Organization communication ; e = Error term

3.8 Ethical Considerations

All responders were asked for their prior consent. Furthermore, the privacy of the information provided in survey answers was maintained. The process of gathering data was entirely optional for the participants. Additionally, there were no derogatory, disrespectful, or personal terms or queries in the research questionnaire.

4. FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 Findings

The research yielded an overall response rate of 61%, which was considered adequate. Male those polled made up 52.5 percent of the investigation, but female participants made up 47.5%. These results unequivocally showed that there is little variation in the gender distribution of National Registration Bureau employees across all departments. The findings showed that 33.3% of the those polled were in the 30- to 39-year-old age range. Of them, 23.1% were between 40 and 49 years old, 22.6% were over 50, and 21.0% were between 18 and 29 years old. This suggests that responders are more inclined to exhibit high levels of maturity, which therefore produces mature answers. Based on the findings, the majority of those taking part (43.1%) listed a bachelor's degree as their greatest educational accomplishment. The remaining respondents' highest academic qualifications were distributed as follows: The majority of them (24.6%) had diplomas as their highest degree, while 20% held postgraduate degrees, and 12.3% had certificates. It was observed that every responder possessed post-secondary educational credentials. This suggested that the majority of respondents met the requirements for the various roles they were holding in terms of instruction. Figure 4 presents the findings. According to the results, the majority of them (33.3%) had been employed for six to ten years in their current roles. The remaining respondents provided information regarding how long they had been in their current positions: 28.2% had been there for 11 to 15 years, 21.5% for 16 years or more, and 17.0% for less than 5 years.

Correlations

The correlation analysis captures the link between the several variables that are being evaluated. Hence, the findings can either be positive or negative or a perfect correlation. Reward policy ($p=0.406$), positive correlation towards the employee performance while organization communication ($p=-0.390$) posted a negative correlation towards the output of the staff. Table 2 displays the results.

Table 1: Correlations

Correlations		Employee Performance	Reward Policy	Organization communication
Employee Performance	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	195		
Reward Policy	Pearson Correlation	.406**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	195	195	
Organization communication	Pearson Correlation	-.390**	-.053	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.248	
	N	195	195	195

** . Correlation (significant 0.01 level 2-tailed).

Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was also employed in the study to ascertain the strength of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. It helped to determine the influence of reward policy, and organization communication on performance of employees. The regression analysis was performed using SPSS. The results are shown below, starting with the ANOVA analysis, moving on to the regression summary, and concluding with the regression coefficients.

Table 3: Regression Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.698 ^a	.487	.55.2	3.53506

a. Predictors: (Constant) reward policy, and organization communication

As seen in Table 3, the regression results suggest an R^2 of 0.562. R Squared describes how much of the variability in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables. This suggests that the four drivers accounted for 48.7% of the difference in performance. The R-squared was modified to 55.2%. This means that the four criteria properly described 55.2% of the overall variability in employee performance. Furthermore, the R value is 0.698. The R number indicates how well the whole model describes the data. In this investigation, the model accounted for 69.8% of the data.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	226.061	4	78.9650	59.023	.000 ^b
	Residual	256.818	90	11.2557		
	Total	482.908	101			

a. Employee performance
b. Predictors: reward policy, and organization communication

The study conducted an analysis of variance (ANOVA). The statistically significant p-value is explained by this investigation. P-values indicate whether the model should be accepted or rejected based on statistical significance. A P-value of less than 0.05 indicates statistical significance for the model. The findings are presented in table 4.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients for the Overall Moderated Model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.623	.521		6.778	.000
Reward Policy	.245	.445	.432	2.214	.001
Organization communication	.345	.066	.241	3.009	.001

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

$$Y = 4.623 + .245 X_1 + .345 X_2$$

The B value of 4.623 is a constant value of employee performance when all determinants are equal to zero as indicated on Table 5. The model indicates that reward policy has a significant effect on employee performance; a unit change in reward policy will result in 0.245-unit or 24.5% change in employee performance, $sig = .001 < .05$, when other variables are held constant. The model indicates that organization communication has a significant effect on employee performance; a unit change in organization communication will result in 0.345-unit or 34.5% change in employee performance, $sig = .000 < .01$, when other variables are held constant.

5. CONCLUSION

The first objective was to evaluate how reward policy affects performance of employees in the public sector in Kenya. The study concluded that a well-structured rewards policy is important for improving employee performance in Kenya's public sector. Employees are motivated when they believe the incentive system is fair, indicative of their contributions, and recognizes their efforts. This sense of justice and appreciation not only improves job satisfaction, but it also motivates people to perform better. Overall, a well-implemented incentive scheme promotes a favorable work atmosphere, resulting in increased productivity and greater devotion to company goals.

The second objective was to examine the effect of organizational communication on performance of employees in the public sector in Kenya. Employee performance improves significantly as a outcome of organizational communication. The study showed that good executive communication is critical to improving employee performance in Kenya's public sector. Employees that are well-informed about organizational performance, receive frequent information, and have open communication lines with management are happier and more productive. Clear and regular communication from managers and supervisors promotes a pleasant work environment in which workers feel appreciated and competent in their positions. This, in turn, leads to increased motivation and organizational performance.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's conclusions have led to the following recommendations to improve worker performance in Kenya's public sector. First, public-sector organizations should emphasize the creation and execution of a clear and equitable incentive strategy that is consistent with employee contributions and industry benchmarks. Regular assessments and adjustments to the reward policy are required to keep it current and competitive. Furthermore, the public sector should consider offering both financial and non-monetary incentives to accommodate a wide range of employee preferences, such as professional prospects for growth, measures for work-life balance, and recognition schemes. Worker involvement in the design and assessment of the incentive system is critical to ensuring that it satisfies their expectations and develops a culture of mutual trust and motivation inside the firm.

It is recommended that a bottom-up method to communication be implemented in Kenya's public sector; this can improve communication between managers and their subordinates, ultimately improving employee performance. This strategy allows for feedback as well as a free flow of ideas between the various levels of an organization or department. Upward communication informs managers and superiors about the extent to which a downward message reached its intended destination and how well it was received and comprehended. Kenya's public sector should have a program of assessing and soliciting input on the methods utilized in its operations. Employees carry out the strategies that the firm implements for its operations, and they are the ones that face the obstacles that these plans may provide. As a result, it is critical that

management regularly assess the plans and get input from employees on these tactics. This enhances both communication and staff performance.

The present research establishes the foundation for further investigations on employee performance in the public sector, emphasizing the importance of rewards, communication, job security, and training. Future research might look at the long-term consequences of these characteristics on staff retention and organizational performance. Furthermore, comparative research across other industries or areas may give more insight into the application of these findings. Researchers might also look at the function of technology in improving organizational communication and training efficacy. Expanding the scope to incorporate additional variables, such as leadership styles or organizational culture, might advance our understanding of the variables influencing employee productivity in the government sector.

According to the research, Kenyan public sector firms should prioritize the creation and implementation of comprehensive incentive plans that are regarded to be fair and in line with employee contributions. To improve communication efficacy, businesses should develop clear and consistent communication channels that keep workers up to speed on organizational issues and provide chances for open conversation with management. To address job security concerns, firms must create clear workforce rules that promote trust and minimize employee worry. Investing in ongoing training and professional development programs is critical. Organizations should focus on creating individualized training programs that address employees' unique requirements, ultimately enhancing their skills and job performance. By addressing these critical areas, Kenyan public sector organizations may build a more engaged, productive, and devoted staff, resulting in organizational success and long-term objectives.

For practice, this study emphasizes the need of well-structured compensation schemes, efficient communication, job stability, and ongoing training in improving employee performance in Kenya's public sector. Organizations should prioritize building equitable and transparent incentive systems that recognize employee accomplishments. Improving communication channels and providing regular, clear information may enhance staff morale and productivity. Furthermore, measures that improve job security can lower anxiety and encourage a positive work atmosphere. Continuous investment in personalized training programs is critical to staff growth and success. By addressing these practical issues, public sector organizations may build a motivated and engaged staff, therefore increasing organizational efficiency and accomplishing long-term goals.

The study recommends conducting similar investigations in other parastatals to enhance the generalizability of the research findings, as the original investigation was limited to the National Registration Bureau in Nairobi. To allow for easy comparison the research findings, the report also suggests that comparable studies be carried out in other ministries around the nation. There is a need for more research on additional aspects that impact employee performance. The study concentrated on four elements (reward policy, and organization communication) which accounted for R²=56.2% affecting employee performance.

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